

Peripheral Ossifying Fibroma in an Uncommon Location: A Case Report of Mandibular Anterior Lingual Gingiva

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Abstract:- Peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF) is a rare, non-neoplastic reactive gingival growth commonly seen in the anterior mandibular region of young adults. It is believed to arise from fibromas that later undergo calcification. Local irritants such as plaque, calculus, trauma and faulty restorations are considered contributing factors. This case report describes a 24-year-old male with an asymptomatic pinkish-red lesion in the mandibular anterior region causing displacement of anterior teeth. Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma, emphasizing the importance of correlating clinical, radiographic and histopathological findings for accurate diagnosis.

Keyword:- Peripheral ossifying Fibroma, Mandible, OPG, Histopathology, surgical excision.

INTRODUCTION:-

In 2005, the World Health Organization classified fibro-osseous lesions of bone into three major categories: fibrous dysplasia, reactive lesions (including periapical cemento-osseous dysplasia, focal cemento-osseous dysplasia & florid cemento-osseous dysplasia) and ossifying fibroma neoplasms¹. Reactive lesions primarily occur in the craniofacial bones and are broadly categorized as central or peripheral types².

This lesion was first described by Shepherd et al. in 1844 as alveolar exostosis and later, in 1972, Eversole and Robin introduced the term peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF)^{3,4}.

Peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF) has been described by several synonyms, including peripheral cemento-ossifying fibroma, ossifying fibro-epithelial polyp, peripheral fibroma with osteogenesis or cementogenesis, calcifying fibroma epulis and calcifying fibroblastic granuloma. Endo et al. attempted to differentiate cemento-ossifying fibroma from ossifying fibroma and fibrous dysplasia through histochemical analysis, reporting that cemento-ossifying fibroma shows positive immunoreactivity for keratan sulfate, whereas ossifying fibroma and fibrous dysplasia demonstrate strong staining for chondroitin-4-sulfate^{3,5,6,7}

POF accounts for approximately 2–9% of all gingival lesions and is considered the third most common localized reactive hyperplastic lesion of the oral cavity, following pyogenic granuloma and peripheral giant cell granuloma^{2,8,9,10}. Nearly 60% of POF cases occur in the maxilla, with about half of these lesions arising in the anterior region^{9,11}. Although the exact etiology of POF remains unclear, two major theories have been proposed regarding its pathogenesis. The first suggests that POF develops from a pyogenic granuloma that subsequently undergoes calcification, while the second proposes that it originates from inflammatory hyperplasia of the periodontal ligament cells⁸.

POF predominantly affects young adults and females, with a higher occurrence in the anterior maxillary region¹². It usually arises from the superficial gingival or interdental tissues as a reactive response to local irritants such as plaque, calculus, orthodontic appliances, ill-fitting prostheses and faulty restorations¹³.

POF commonly presents as a solitary, slow-growing nodular lesion that may be either pedunculated or sessile¹⁴. The overlying mucosa is generally smooth or occasionally ulcerated, with a pink to reddish appearance^{15,16}. In some cases, tooth migration and interdental bone destruction have also been reported. Although POF is usually less than 1.5 cm in diameter, larger lesions measuring up to 6 cm and 9 cm have been documented^{17,18}.

Clinical features alone are insufficient for the diagnosis of POF, as several lesions such as pyogenic granuloma and peripheral giant cell granuloma may present with similar clinical characteristics and progression. Therefore, definitive diagnosis requires biopsy and histopathological examination. The histopathological features of POF show a broad spectrum and have been extensively described by Buchner et al¹⁵.

POF typically occurs as a solitary gingival growth. In this report we present rare case of POF location affecting the mandibular lingual gingiva and sulcus area of 24-year old male.

CASE REPORT:-

A 24year old Male patient reported to the department of Oral Medicine and Radiology with chief complaint of painless growth over lower front region of jaw since, 1 year. fig (1 & 2).

FIG 1 & 2- Clinical presentation showing well-defined soft tissue overgrowth with respect 31,32,41,42,43

The patient had been managed previously by many physician and dental specialists for the same complaint, but the lesion were recurrent. the lesion was asymptomatic, appeared more than one year ago, and had been increasing gradually in size. The family history revealed no genetic condition.

A Single nodular growth was present on lingual surface of mandibular anterior region of size 3X4 cm in diameter extending M/L – from cingulum of 32 To distal of 43, S/I – from incisal edge to lingual sulcus. It was on a broad base connected, with the sublingual anatomical region. The shape of the lesion was roughly oval, surface was smooth with glossy appearance and no ulcerations seen. colour was pinkish bright red. Consistency was Soft on incisal, cingulum area & firm toward lingual sulcus. There was bleeding spots present on surface of lesion. Absent any discharge from the lesion during palpation. Tenderness was absent. Patient give no history of trauma, burning sensation, bleeding or discharge is reported.

Based on the patient's history and clinical examination, a provisional diagnosis of fibroma and differential diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma, pyogenic granuloma, peripheral giant cell granuloma was given.

Figure 3 Orthopantomogram

Orthopantomogram (OPG), Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) and Incisional biopsy were performed.

On radiographic investigation, orthopantomogram radiograph shows soft tissue shadow involving between 31,32,41,42 (fig3). The panoramic view showed generalized horizontal bone loss along with periapical radiolucency with respect to 41 and radiolucency at coronal portion of 46 involving enamel and dentin.

Figure 4. Axial View

Figure 5. Coronal View

An axial CBCT image showing soft tissue shadow involving mandibular anterior.(fig. 4) In A coronal CBCT image shows round radiolucency at cervical portion of 41 s/o internal resorption also, radiolucency at apical portion of 41(fig 5).

Figure 6: Histopathological picture showing fibroblastic stroma with varying cellularity.

On histopathologic examination, fibro- cellular collagen tissue bundles covered with hyper parakeratnised epithelium with rete ridges. the connective tissue stroma reveals area of ossification and rich vascularity, endothelial cell proliferation and inflammatory cell infiltrate. Additionally, many well-defined cementum-like elements were observed scattered throughout the stroma in the form of ossicles. There were also many blood arteries with RBCs extravasated in them. The stratified squamous epithelium above was hyperplastic and hyperparakeratinized. (fig 6)

Histological, radiological and clinical examinations have led to the final diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma.

TREATMENT:-

The treatment of peripheral ossifying fibroma using surgical excision, under aseptic conditions, local anesthesia was administered. flap was raised using No. 15 blade. Excision of the lesion was done, irrigation was done at the surgical site, hemostasis was achieved. Suturing was done using interrupted sutures. Post operative instructions were given. Patient gives fallow up after 15 days of excision (fig 7 & 8).

Fig No. 7 & 8 - Follow up after 15 days image showing complete healing.

DISCUSSION:-

Peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF) is a reactive, non-neoplastic gingival overgrowth that has been well documented in the literature since the late 1940s¹⁹. Over time, it has been described by several terms such as epulis²⁰, peripheral fibroma with calcification, calcifying fibroblastic granuloma^{14,21}, peripheral cementifying fibroma²² and peripheral cemento-ossifying fibroma²³. Despite the varied terminology POF is now recognized as a distinct clinicopathological entity that predominantly originates from the periodontal ligament²⁴. Ossifying fibromas commonly occur in the craniofacial region and are broadly classified into central and peripheral types. The central variant arises from the endosteum or periodontal ligament near the root apex and expands from the medullary cavity of the bone, whereas the peripheral variant develops within the soft tissues overlying the alveolar process²⁶.

POF predominantly affects the anterior maxillary region, particularly the incisor-cuspid area and is more commonly seen in females during the second and third decades of life^{26,27,28}. Hormonal influences have been proposed as a possible contributing factor due to its female predominance and higher incidence during adolescence and early adulthood¹². Nevertheless, cases involving males and older individuals have also been documented.

The etiopathogenesis of POF is not clearly understood; however, chronic irritation and trauma are considered the primary contributing factors. Local irritants including dental plaque, calculus, microorganisms, faulty restorations, masticatory trauma and ill-fitting prostheses may stimulate the periodontal ligament, resulting in reactive hyperplasia²⁹. The exclusive occurrence of POF on the gingiva and its close relationship with the periodontal ligament further support its periodontal ligament origin¹⁹. Eversole and Rovin also proposed that POF may initially develop as a pyogenic granuloma, which later undergoes fibrous maturation and calcification¹⁴.

Clinically, POF is usually asymptomatic, sessile or pedunculated gingival mass²⁰ and slow growing, although larger lesions may cause displacement of adjacent teeth and functional discomfort. POF may present either as a pedunculated nodule or as a lesion with a broad sessile base. The surface can be smooth or irregular and the color typically varies from pink to red or bright red, often with areas of ulceration. Most lesions are smaller than 2 cm in diameter^{15,13}; however, larger lesions measuring up to 9 cm^{15,20} have also been reported. The size of POF may range from a few millimeters to several centimeters. Although uncommon, some cases may show underlying bone resorption and displacement of adjacent teeth¹⁷.

Radiographic findings in POF are usually insignificant; however, occasional features such as superficial bone erosion, interdental bone loss, or displacement of adjacent teeth may be evident^{17,19,20}. Histopathologically, POF consists of a non-encapsulated fibrocellular connective tissue stroma covered by stratified squamous epithelium, which may show ulceration in some cases^{15,20,21}. The lesion typically demonstrates varying degrees of calcification, including dystrophic calcifications, cementum-like deposits and areas of woven or lamellar bone formation³⁰.

The differential diagnosis of POF includes pyogenic granuloma, peripheral giant cell granuloma, traumatic fibroma and peripheral odontogenic fibroma. Histological examination is essential to distinguish POF from peripheral odontogenic fibroma, which is considered a true odontogenic neoplasm containing odontogenic epithelium and dysplastic dentin. Accurate diagnosis therefore requires careful correlation of clinical, radiographic and histopathological findings^{15,30}.

Management of POF involves complete surgical excision of the lesion along with elimination of local etiological factors through scaling and root planing of adjacent teeth^{15,20}. Excision should include the involved periosteum and periodontal ligament to reduce the risk of recurrence. Recurrence rates ranging from 8% to 20% have been reported in the literature¹⁴, which may be attributed to incomplete excision, persistent local irritants or difficulty in accessing interdental lesions during surgery⁹. Therefore, long-term follow-up is essential for early detection and management of recurrent lesions³¹.

CONCLUSION:-

In conclusion, peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF) is a slow-growing reactive lesion with limited growth potential and is often asymptomatic, leading to delayed presentation and treatment. Clinically, POF should be considered in young patients presenting with a gradually enlarging pink soft tissue nodule, particularly in the anterior maxillary or gingival region. In the present case, the lesion involved the interdental papillae of 31, 32, 33, 41, 42 and 43 extending into the lingual sulcus and appeared pinkish-red with a soft to firm consistency. The diagnosis of POF was confirmed through histopathological and radiographic evaluation. Surgical excision was performed as the treatment modality, followed by regular postoperative follow-up and monitoring to evaluate healing and detect any recurrence.

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